

**BAZALI YER TEKISLAGICH DISKLI YUMSHATKICHINI
TEKISLAGICH KOVSHIGA NISBATAN O'RNATILISH MASOFASINI
UNING ISH KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI O'RGANISH**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yer tekislash mashinasiga o'rnatilgan diskli yumshatkichning ish texnologiyasi va tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatish masofasini nazariy tadqiqotlar natijasidan kelib chiqib, tajriba asosida aniqlangan ko'rsatkichlari asoslangan holda keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tuproq, tekislagich, yumshatkich, kovsh, gradus, burchak, uvalanish, notekislik, qarshilik, agregat, tezlik.

Abstract: This article presents the working technology of the disc softener installed on the leveling machine and the parameters of the installation distance in relation to the leveler bucket, based on the results of theoretical studies and experimentally determined parameters.

Key words: Soil, leveler, softener, scoop, grade, angle, slope, unevenness, resistance, aggregate, speed.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена технология работы дискового умягчителя, установленного на грунтопланировочной машине, и параметры установочного расстояния относительно планировочного ковша на основе результатов теоретических исследований и экспериментально определенных параметров.

Ключевые слова: Почва, выравнитель, смягчитель, совок, сорт, угол, уклон, неровности, сопротивление, заполнитель, скорость.

Jahonda qishloq xo'jalik ekinlarining urug'larini ekish uchun yerlarni tekislashning resurstejamkor texnologiyalari va ularni amalga oshiradigan texnika vositalarining yangi namunalarini yaratish, mavjud mashinalarni ish jarayonida resurstejamkorligini ta'minlash maqsadida takomillashtirishning ilmiy-texnikaviy asoslarini ishlab chiqishga yo'naltirilgan maqsadli ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari olib borilmoqda.

Bazali yer tekislagichlar hamda diskli ish organlariga ega bo'lgan tuproqqa ishlov berish mashinalarini yaratish va ularning parametrlarini asoslash, shuningdek disk bilan tuproqning o'zaro ta'sirlashish jarayonlari bo'yicha xorijda X.Li, D.Zang, F.Amran, O.Omafunnei, K.Wasfy, H.Harrison, W.Gill, C.Reavers, A.Bailey, R.Godwin, D.Seig, M.Alfott, M.Alam, J.Balloch, R.Reeder, A.Naim, S.Sulaiman, R.Davies, G.N.Sineokov, V.F.Strelbiskiy, F.M.Kanarev, P.S.Nartov, G.Teslyuk, Ye.V. Antonov va boshqalar tomonidan tadqiqotlar o'tkazilgan.

Ushbu yo'nalishda respublikamizda disk bilan ishlov berish va yer tekislagichlar bo'yicha M.A.Axmedjanov, N.P.Samsonova, I.P.Bratshev,

E.N.Kuzina, I.A.Babadjanov, A.E.Teshaboev, G.N.Kim, P.G.Hikmatov, I.S.Hasanov, F.M.Mamatov, A.To'xtaqo'ziev, S.P.Chirsov, A.N.Xudoyorov, B.Xushvaqto'v, H.T.Qirg'izov, A.R.Normirzaev, B.M.Xudayarov, M.M.Ergashev va boshqa olimlar tomonidan ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari olib borilgan.

Shu bilan birga yer tekislash mashinalarini takomillashtirish va ularning ish samaradorligini oshirish hozirgi kunning dolzarb masalalaridan biri hisoblanadi. Olib borilgan tadqiqot ishlarida bazali yer tekislash mashinalariga o'rnatilgan diskli yumshatkichlarning nazariy tadqiqotlari asosida ularni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatish masofalarini aniqlash bo'yicha tala tajriba tadqiqotlari olib borildi. Tajribalar 6 va 8 km/soat tezliklarda o'tkazildi. Bunda diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi 25 sm interval bilan 50 sm dan 125 sm gacha o'zgartirildi. Bunda diskli yumshatkichlarni harakat yo'nalishiga nisbatan o'rnatilish burchagi, ular orasidagi ko'ndalang masofa hamda ularga beriladigan tik yuklanish o'zgarma va mos ravishda 30° , 25 sm va 1,0 kN/m ga teng etib qabul qilindi.

Asosiy ko'rsatkichlar sifatida tuproqning uvalanish sifati, ishlov berilgan dala yuzasidagi notekisliklarning balandligi hamda qurilmaning tortishga qarshiligi olindi.

Tajribalarda olingan natijalar 1-jadval va 1.2-3-rasmlarda keltirilgan. Tajribalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, har ikkala harakat tezligida ham diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasining ortishi tuproqning uvalanish sifatini yaxshilanishiga olib kelgan, ya'ni o'lchami 50 mm dan katta bo'lgan tuproq fraksiyalarining miqdori kamayib, o'lchami 25 mm dan kichik bo'lgan tuproq fraksiyalari miqdori ortgan. Buni diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi ortishi bilan disklar tomonidan tuproqqa tekislagich kovshi yetib kelmasdan ishlov berilishi ta'minlanishi bilan izohlash mumkin.

Diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi ortishi bilan dala yuzasidagi notekisliklarning balandliklari oldin kamaygan, keyin esa ortgan, tuproqning uvalanish sifati yaxshilangan, tortishga solishtirma qarshilik esa kamaygan. Buni quyidagicha izohlash mumkin: birinchidan shuni ta'kidlash lozimki, diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi 50 va 75 sm bo'lganda diskli yumshatkichlarni tuproq bilan ta'sir vaqti kamayishi oqibatida tekislagich kovshi oldida tuproqning uyulish hollari kuzatildi va natijada ular tekislagich tomonidan yetarli darajada maydalanmay va tekislanmay qoldi, ikkinchidan yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi ortishi bilan uning tuproq bo'laklariga ta'sir vaqti ortadi va natijada uning yanada maydalanishi va tekislanishi ta'minlanadi.

Diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi 100 va 125 sm bo'lganda ishlov berilgan dala yuzasidagi notekisliklarning balandliklari unga qo'yilgan talablarga mos keldi. Bazali tekislagichning tekislash sifati yaxshilanib tuproq fraksiyasi yaxshilanib borilgan.

1 – jadval.

**Diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o‘rnatilish masofa L_b
 ni ularning ish ko‘rsatkichlariga ta’siri**

Diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o‘rnatilish masofa, sm	Tuproq fraksiyalarining ulushi, %			Ishlov berilgan dala yuzasidagi notekisliklarning balandligi, sm	Diskli yumshatkichlarning tortishga solishtirma qarshiligi, kN/m
	fraksiyalar o‘lchamlari, mm				
	>50	50-25	<25		
<i>V=6 km/soat</i>					
50	1,5	21,1	77,4	4,8	1,89
75	1,6	19,0	79,4	4,38	1,56
100	1,5	17,8	80,7	3,95	1,22
125	1,0	18,1	80,9	3,9	1,20
<i>V=8 km/soat</i>					
50	1,2	20,3	78,5	5,1	2,04
75	1,3	18,6	80,1	4,7	1,67
100	1,1	17,9	82,0	4,21	1,41
125	0,7	17,2	82,1	4,07	1,37

1 va 2 – agregat harakat tezligi mos ravishda 6,0 va 8,0 km/soat

1-rasm. Tuproqning uvalanish darajasi ($F_{<50}$) ni diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o‘rnatilish masofasi (L) ga bog‘liq ravishda o‘zgarish grafigi

1 va 2 – agregat harakat tezligi mos ravishda 6,0 va 8,0 km/soat

2-rasm. Ishlov berilgan qatlam yuzasidagi notekisliklarning balandligi (h_a) ni diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o‘rnatilish masofasi (L) ga bog‘liq ravishda o‘zgarish grafiglari

1 va 2 – agregat harakat tezligi mos ravishda 6,0 va 9,0 km/soat

3-rasm. Qurilmaning tortishga solishtirma qarshiligi (R) ni diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi (L) ga bog'liq ravishda o'zgarish grafigi

Qurilmaning tortishga solishtirma qarshiligi diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi ortishi bilan kamaygan. Masalan, agregatning har ikkala harakat tezligida ham ta'kidlangan masofa 50 sm dan 125 sm gacha o'zgariganda qurilmaning solishtirma qarshiligi mos ravishda 0,69 kN va 0,67 kN ga kamaygan. Buning asosiy sababi shuki, bu masofa 50 sm bo'lganda diskli yumshatkichlar tomonidan tuproq bo'laklariga tekislagich kovshi yetib kelmasdan ishlov berilishi ta'minlanmasligi bilan tushuntirish mumkin. Bu masofa ortishi bilan esa yuqoridagi kamchilik bartaraf etiladi va tortishga solishtirma qarshilik ham kamayib boradi.

2 va 3-rasmlarda keltirilgan grafik bog'lanishlarni yuqorida ta'kidlangan usul qo'llanilib topilgan quyidagi empirik formulalar bilan ifodalash mumkin:

a) agregat harakat tezligi 6 km/soat bo'lgan hol uchun

$$F_{<50} = 70,52 + 0,173L \quad (R^2 = 0,999), \% \quad (1)$$

$$h_d = 6,370 - 0,038L \quad (R^2 = 0,985), \text{ sm} \quad (2)$$

$$R = 3,169 - 0,031L \quad (R^2 = 0,984), \text{ kN/m} \quad (3)$$

b) agregat harakat tezligi 8 km/soat bo'lgan hol uchun

$$F_{<50} = 72,10 + 0,155L \quad (R^2 = 0,975), \% \quad (4)$$

$$h_d = 6,488 - 0,032L \quad (R^2 = 0,985), \text{ sm} \quad (5)$$

$$R = 3,327 - 0,032L \quad (R^2 = 0,997), \text{ kN/m} \quad (6)$$

bunda L –diskli yumshatkichlarga beriladigan solishtirma tik yuklanish (L =50-125 sm oralig'ida). Olib borilgan tajribalar shuni xulosa qilish mumkinki, diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi kamida 100 sm bo'lishi lozim. Bunda tekislash texnologik jarayonni kam energiya sarflagan holda yuqori ish sifatini ta'minlashi uchun diskli yumshatkichlarni tekislagich kovshiga nisbatan o'rnatilish masofasi kamida 100 sm bo'lishi aniqlandi.

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